

**VISUAL AIDS, WHICH ARE USED IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS
IN THE USE OF DIDACTIC GAMES**

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ABSTRACT In this article, it is emphasized that the education of mature, educated young people in all respects, the dependence of the level of knowledge and skills given to the students, the use of non-traditional materials in the lessons will have a positive effect on the course transition.

KEYWORDS Active, generalization, reinforcement, unconventional, interactive, innovative, method, conference, lesson, fiction, Multimedia, native language, word, exercise, education, education, system, problem.

INTRODUCTION

Any, beautiful in all respects, brought into the class room, the visual, which can attract the attention of the child, also makes the child without any tongue enter the language, forcing him to think. The use of hand-crafted visual weapons in the 2nd grades is especially important. Primary school teachers themselves can prepare visual weapons on a variety of topics.

Making weapons with hand-held sights is diverse. For the cultivation of oral speech of readers, a large amount of colorful paintings, booklets and hand-made materials are prepared. We can also prepare various layouts and moving toys for the lessons of mother tongue, reading, mathematics. Different cards are important when it comes to growing, motivating thinking and growing interest in the activities of students at a young age. The use of didactic materials increase the student's interest in the lessons, kengaytiradi the scope of knowledge. It nurtures the features of ingenuity in them, strengthens memory and helps to remember the learned material for a long time.

If it is possible for the child to perceive, see the same thing with his eyes, hold it with a hand, sniff if the smell, if possible, taste tastier, then the same subject and its character, properties will not be forgotten by the reader. In these types of perception, the reader's perception of vision, knowledge of smell, perception, taste are involved.

A clever teacher uses in each lesson a wide range of distributed vocabulary, pictorial, didactic materials, syllabic, colloquial cards, letters, word boxes.

1. It provides a thorough examination of the knowledge of students by showing them exactly the specific visions of the subjects studied in the lesson, for example, birds, animals, makiab, class, cities and so on, which can be seen directly by himself. It is possible to recall what they saw in the lesson, linking them to the content of the subject studied through questions and answers.

2. The use of models of various technical tools that correspond to the content of the subject under study:

- The use of images in the study of materials on things that can be seen by eye in some cities and villages, in general, at the same time.
- The use of different types of Cards (For example: pictures can be depicted or made in the form of different fruits, animals). This is a common form of blindness, which is used in the lessons of mother tongue and reading.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The types of instruction are different, we can continue it again. Another of the improvised means is a make-up of a hand-made apple tree. On the tree hang berries. In the process of the game, we divide the class into three groups. One reader is removed from each group. Students must break through the fruits and complete the task behind him. Behind each fruit will be given words related to the subject. Students should compose a sentence in which this word is involved and write it on a blackboard. The game continues thus, which is the same group wins if the group collects more apple fruit.

It is known that the game takes the main place in the activities of the child, who, having passed the 2nd grade, took the first step to the threshold of the school. The game is their most favorite pastime, and they try to harmonize any training with the game.

Therefore, the teacher makes it possible to increase the effectiveness of the educational process by using the activities of the pupil in their hobby — without squeezing the game, but with the proper use of it for the purpose.

Didactic games used in the educational process can be classified into 2 types according to the content and the form of implementation we have.

„POSTMAN”

One of the students comes into the class as a postman, and the students are given a letter with a photo of one. Each reader will tell what is depicted in the photo in his hand. Other readers list how many words their comrades used throughout the story. The reader who used a lot of words and with Orin is considered a winner.

„DAY AND NIGHT”

The teacher writes two or more words on the blackboard. After the students read, they give the command "night". Children close their eyes and put themselves to sleep. The teacher alternates a letter or a syllable in words. After the command "day", the readers open their eyes and determine what changes were made.

Option 1: Karima-Salima, Cathedral-hour, took-stayed.

Option 2: children-Bolaris, Sheriff-scarf, Ham-mining.

Option 3: day-Beaver, sand—tail, pupil - pilot, day-night.

CONCLUSION

The fact that the child will remember what he saw will depend on the fact that the sighted weapons will be treated with taste. If junior schoolchildren are not taught the methods of memorization, then in such cases the level of direct exposure of children to the material will stop for a long time.

In the process of didactic games, it is extremely useful for the reader to tell the contents of the picture. Therefore, the teacher must show a personal example, telling Live, interesting in the language of literature through painting. Hand-held materials, photos and visual weapons on the head increase the activity of pupils.

REFERENCES

1. Adizova N. "The role of ethnotoponym in the toponym of bukhara District" International Scientific Journal Theoretical & Applied Science p-ISSN: 2308-4944 (print) e-ISSN: 2409-0085 (online) Year: 2020 Issue: 01 Volume: 81 Published: 30.01.2020 <http://T-Science.org> 414-416
2. Adizova N. Nominal description of the bukhara district. International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE) ISSN:2277-3878 Volume-, Issue-3S, October 2019.
3. Adizova N. The Main Motives and Objectives of fun genre in folklore. International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE) ISSN: 2277-3878, Volume-8, Issue-3S, October 2019. –P.202-207.
4. Косимов Ф. М., Ярашов М. Ж. ТВОРЧЕСКИЕ САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНЫЕ РАБОТЫ НА УРОКАХ МАТЕМАТИКИ В НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССАХ //ИННОВАЦИОННЫЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ РАЗВИТИЯ НАУКИ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ: ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ. – 2020. – С. 178-181.
5. Rustamova G. B. THE INTERPRETATION OF THE WILLOW IMAGE IN UZBEK FOLKLORE //ЛУЧШАЯ НАУЧНАЯ СТАТЬЯ 2020. – 2020. – С. 53-57.
6. Raximqulovich, Ismatov Sobirjon; ,METHODS OF WORKING WITH TEXT IN LITERARY READING LESSONS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL,EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research,1,,345-347,2020,EPRA Publishing